

The Construction of a Mind Confused Society: Complexity and the Searching for Means

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ABSTRACT

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Political science is an important discipline that studies the political thoughts, values and ideologies of societies. However, the concept of cognitive fuzziness points to an important problem in this field. Confusion includes factors that cause people's thinking on political issues to become ambiguous, complex or difficult to understand. In this article, we will discuss the factors that influence the formation of confusion in political science and the consequences of these factors. The concept of confused society refers to the complexity of social relations and difficulties in understanding reality. With the development of social structures, cultural diversity and communication technologies, societies are becoming more and more complex, while individuals make more and more efforts to understand the facts. Mental fuzziness in a society can be caused by a combination of many different factors. These factors can include political tensions, economic uncertainty, social transformations, cultural differences or technological speed. In a confused society, conflicts between people can increase, disagreements can intensify and it can be difficult to create a shared vision or value system. On the other hand, in a confused society, communication problems can also be widespread. Conflicts between people may become difficult to resolve and social cohesion and solidarity may decrease. It is

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therefore important to promote transparent communication and understanding in order for society to become healthier and more adaptive. This concept can be used to understand the state of a society and identify potential problems. It is important in a society

with a clouded mind to make efforts to find solutions and improve social relations. In doing so, strengthening values such as tolerance, empathy and cooperation can help to build a healthier society.

INTRODUCTION

Political science is an important discipline that studies the political thoughts, values and ideologies of societies. However, the concept of cognitive blurring points to an important problem in this field. Mental fuzziness includes factors that cause people's thinking on political issues to become ambiguous, complex or difficult to understand. In this article, the factors that influence the formation of fuzziness in political science will be discussed along with their culprits. While political science includes different approaches to evidence-based social inquiry, each of its traditions is rational and rule-bound, and thus seeks to produce knowledge in a rigorous manner. These common qualities allow us to use a common vocabulary to describe elements of transparency and society. The main motivation for increasing transparency is intellectual. Despite the heterogeneity of the discipline, all evidence-based approaches to social inquiry in political science share a number of common features that allow them to benefit from transparency. In other words, all empirical political science research - and social inquiry more broadly - has common features that transparency illuminates and enhances, and common concerns that transparency addresses. Accordingly, all such research can benefit from community practices that promote transparency. We define social research as a process that entails collecting and analyzing information about the social world in order to produce valid knowledge claims. Social research has at least three constitutive dimensions. First, each research tradition is founded on reasons, a set of shared beliefs about the social world and how it can be known. Second, each of these foundations implies prescriptive rules that constitute a toolbox of methods and norms that guide the collection and analysis of knowledge about the

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social world. Third, the value that can potentially be derived from research conducted by members of any research community depends on that work being rigorously conducted in accordance with the relevant rules. Members of research communities share epistemological beliefs about how best to understand and explain certain aspects of the social world, namely causes. These commitments inform researchers' views on what knowledge is (and is not) and how knowledge claims are constructed. This characterization does not require that the beliefs of a knowledge community have a specific content. Different communities have their own understandings of how knowledge should be identified, collected, interpreted, transformed into analyzable form and analyzed in order to draw valid evidence-based conclusions about the social world. For a given research community to engage in social inquiry, it is enough to have shared views about what intersubjective knowledge is and how it is produced. The reason-oriented foundations of social inquiry may be easier to see in evidence-based approaches that provide a formal description of the logic underlying inquiry and the inferential or interpretive rules that accompany it. Take, for example, the potential consequences approach, which argues that while the world is characterized by causal regularities, identifying them is hampered by the fundamental problem of causal inference (Rubin 1974, Pearl 2009). Academics cannot see the world with and without a putative cause of a given outcome at the same time. They are therefore limited in what kinds of claims they can make about cause and effect. One approach to addressing this fundamental problem is to generate observations that can reveal whether the assumed causal relationships exist or not. Another is to find situations in which these observations occur naturally.

Epistemic foundations can also be recognized when they are less formally articulated or implicit. For example, even before more careful explanations of the logical foundations of process tracing began to emerge (Bennett 2015; Fairfield & Charman 2015, 2017; Humphreys & Jacobs 2015; Waldner 2015), scholars have argued that there is a formal logic underlying the method (Mahoney 2012, 583). In this context, the phrase "fuzzy society" is probably used to describe a society that is complex, ambiguous and difficult to understand. To generalize briefly, the phrase is used to describe a situation where ideas, beliefs and values in society are unclear, contradictory or ambiguous. Mental confusion in a society can be caused by a combination of many different factors. These factors may include political tensions, economic uncertainty, social transformations, cultural differences or technological speed. In a

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fuzzy society, conflicts between people can increase, disagreements can intensify and it can be difficult to create a shared vision or value system. On the other hand, in a fuzzy society, communication problems may also be common. Conflicts between people may become more difficult to resolve and social cohesion and solidarity may decrease. It is therefore important to promote transparent communication and understanding in order to promote a healthier and more cohesive society.

PURPOSE

The concept of a confused society refers to the complexity of social relations and the difficulties in understanding reality. With the development of social structures, cultural diversity and communication technologies, societies are becoming more and more complex, and individuals are making greater efforts to understand reality. Political science is an important discipline that studies the political thoughts, values and ideologies of societies. However, the concept of confusion points to an important problem in this field. Mental fuzziness includes factors that cause people's thinking on political issues to become ambiguous, complex or difficult to understand. This paper will discuss the factors that influence the formation of mental fuzziness in political science and analyze the concept of the construction of a fuzzy society, the factors affecting a fuzzy society and its consequences.

METHOD

Research; The Construction of a Confused Society: Social Complexity and the Search for Meaning was originally written as a review article through a literature review of Turkish and foreign sources.

FINDINGS

In the literature, the term Mental Confused Society and the cause-and-effect processes of

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Building a Confused Society are used to understand the current state of a society and to identify potential problems. In a blurred society, it is important to find solutions and make efforts to improve social relations. In doing so, strengthening values such as tolerance, empathy and cooperation can help society to achieve a healthier structure (Bennett 2015; Fairfield & Charman 2015, 2017; Humphreys & Jacobs 2015; Waldner 2015; Cevizoğlu 2021). The term "Mind Confused Society" has also been used to describe a society in which people's thoughts and emotional states are not clear, where uncertainty and confusion prevail; these terms describe a complex and troubled social structure that is often caused by problems such as miscommunication, disagreement, lack of tolerance. In Marxist thought, a "confused society" refers to capitalist society's manipulation of individuals' thoughts, ideologies and consciousness to mislead them about their real situation (Marx 2015; Marx 1992). It describes a society in which society is intellectually influenced and individuals are misinformed about their real situation through media, advertising and ideological pressure. Different intellectual approaches such as cultural theory, postmodernism or critical theory emphasize the diversity and ambiguity of social realities under this concept, arguing that the meaning of social structures is ambiguous and complex (Smith 2007; Wertsch, 2015; Zobar 2019).

Factors in the Formation of Mental Confusion in Political Science and the Global Examples

The concept of "Building a Confused Society" refers to the complexity of social relations and the difficulties in understanding reality. This concept refers to the blurring of reality in societies as a result of the interaction of social, cultural and political factors and people having different perspectives. From a sociological point of view, this concept explains the meaning structure of society, forms of communication and the way people perceive the world. The concept of the construction of a confused society is of great importance for understanding society's understanding and access to information. Understanding this concept is important to reduce societal opacity, recognize manipulation and help individuals develop more critical thinking skills.

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Throughout the world, the influence of the media and the development of communication technologies are influencing the construction of a mind-blurred society. The interaction between different cultures, beliefs and opinions leads to understanding facts from different perspectives. While the influence of media and politics shapes the way society understands facts, the rapid flow of information brought about by the digital age can also pave the way for the spread of misleading information. In the case of Turkey, historical, cultural and political diversity affects the construction of a confused society. Conflicts between different ethnic groups, cultural perspectives and political views can lead to opacification of facts. The political influence of the media can limit the way society understands facts. At the same time, however, increased information sharing among individuals and different voices being heard through the influence of social media can contribute to more perspectives being taken into account.

The construction of a fuzzy society is important for political scientists in terms of the shaping of social views and the meaning of political participation. How political leaders and parties represent different perspectives, how the media reflects political discourse, and how society understands political realities are critical for analyzing political processes. By understanding the construction of an opaque society, political scientists seek to better understand the impact of political campaigns, voter behavior and democratic processes. Political scientists also work to develop political reforms and communication strategies to reduce social opacity and increase access to information. The term "building a confused society" is a concept used to describe a society in which people's thoughts and opinions are formed in a vague, complex or difficult to understand way, often due to a lack of communication, information flow and intellectual clarity. It refers to a situation in which the ability of individuals and society in general to think, understand and communicate clearly and unambiguously is weakened and can be the result of various factors such as Information Pollution, Communication Inadequacy, Multiple Perspectives, Difficulty Filtering Information, Manipulation and Propaganda. Among these factors, information pollution can be explained as the muddying of people's thoughts due to the difficulty of distinguishing between true and false information in our age full of resources such as the internet and social media. On the other hand, the lack of effective communication between people can lead to an increase in confusion and differences of opinion and negatively affect the intellectual clarity of society. Other factors in the formation of societies that we can characterize as "confused" can be briefly summarized as;

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the difficulty of forming a common understanding on social issues due to the presence of many different views and perspectives in society due to different cultures, beliefs and values, easy access to information makes it difficult to evaluate the accuracy and reliability of information at the same time and the complexity this creates in minds, the influence of people's thoughts through misleading or deliberately false information and propaganda, and the uncertainty that occurs in society. From a political science perspective, mental fuzziness includes factors that cause people's thinking on political issues to become uncertain, complex or difficult to understand. In this context, the factors and their effects that can be mentioned to understand the concept of mental confusion in political science can be summarized as follows:

-Disagreement and Ideological Diversity: Different political views, values and ideologies can exist within society. These differences can obscure people's thinking on political issues and cause confusion.

-Media and Information Flow: The media plays an important role in the dissemination of political issues. However, there can be problems with the reliability and diversity of information in the media, which can affect the public's ability to understand and evaluate political issues.

-Populism and Manipulation: Political populism and manipulation can influence people's political views and blur the boundaries between reality and perception.

-Communication Barriers: The complexity of political issues can make it difficult for people to communicate with each other. Lack of communication or misunderstandings can lead to confusion.

-Cultural and Historical Context: Political views are shaped by cultural and historical context. Complexity in this context can make political ideas difficult to understand.

-Information Pollution and Fake News: Fake news and misleading information can cause

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confusion on political issues. People may find it difficult to distinguish between truth and misinformation.

In political science, the construction of a confused society can make it difficult for democratic processes to function properly. Therefore, solutions such as media literacy, critical thinking and the promotion of political participation can help to clarify society's political thinking and build better political communication. In the context of global examples, there are situations and regions around the world where societies experience political, cultural, social and communicative confusion. Although these situations may be caused by different factors and each may involve its own specific conditions, we can summarize the global examples of the occurrence of confusion in political science under the following headings:

Differences of Opinion and Ideological Diversity:

The divergent views of different political parties and groups in a country can complicate public opinion on political issues. Different cultural values and beliefs can differentiate the way society understands political issues. For example, differences in political views between Democrats and Republicans in the United States have complicated public thinking on political issues; the Israeli-Palestinian conflict in the Middle East has led to political confusion due to cultural and ideological differences.

Media and Information Exchange:

When a news channel emphasizes a particular political view, the media can influence public opinion and lead to confusion. Misleading news spreading rapidly on social media can make it difficult for the public to understand the facts. For example, in Brazil, populist leader Jair Bolsonaro's efforts to manipulate the media made it difficult for the public to understand political realities. During the Ukraine-Russia crisis, different news narratives between media outlets in different countries affected the international public's understanding of the facts.

Populism and Manipulation:

Emotional rhetoric by a political leader can cause the public to question the facts and complicate political thinking. Propaganda campaigns can influence people's views on political issues and blur the boundaries between reality and perception. In Turkey, for example, populist rhetoric by political leaders and media manipulation have influenced the public's political thinking, leading to confusion. In the Philippines, Rodrigo Duterte's hardline populist policies have distorted political realities and confused the public mind.

Communication Barriers:

Lack of communication between people from different languages and cultures can obscure public opinion on political issues. Misunderstandings between parties during a debate can lead to confusion. In this context, global examples include the lack of communication in India due to different languages and cultures, which has led to disagreements by obscuring society's thinking on political issues, or the communication difficulties between countries within the European Union, which complicates political cooperation and leads to confusion.

Cultural and Historical Context:

Deep conflicts or events in a society's history can influence political views and lead to confusion. Different cultural values can make political issues difficult to understand and complicate societal views. For example, the November War between India and Pakistan and regional historical conflicts have complicated societies' political views and caused confusion. On the other hand, the Brexit process in Europe has complicated political views due to the historical and cultural contexts of different countries.

Disinformation and Fake News:

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Fake news spread during an election period can distort the public's political opinions and lead to confusion. The use of misleading statistics or data can make it difficult for people to understand the facts. Global examples include the spread of misleading information about the state of the Amazon forests in Brazil, which distorts the public's political opinions and causes confusion, or the spread of misleading information and fake news among political parties during election periods in Turkey, which affects voters' views on political issues and causes political confusion.

The examples are significant in that they show that confused societies may be caused by different reasons and manifest in different ways for different regions around of the world. They illustrate how each factor can influence how political fuzziness develops. Each factor can, in different ways, complicate and reduce clarity in public political thinking. In political science, political fuzziness is a phenomenon that complicates societies' efforts to understand political issues. Factors such as differences of opinion, media influence, manipulation and communication gaps can all contribute to this. Global examples show that confusion can occur in different societies under a variety of circumstances. Therefore, more attention needs to be paid to areas such as communication, media and education to improve clarity on political issues.

Theoretical Approaches:

The concept of "the construction of a confused society" is a more commonly used expression which cannot be traced back to a specific source, and there is no clear history or first use by a specific person. The concept has become popular over time and has been used by different people in different contexts. However, similar concepts or ideas have been addressed throughout history by social scientists and thinkers interested in communication, information flow and social change. For example, ideas such as Marshall McLuhan's (2020) concept of the "Global Village" or Jean Baudrillard's relationship between reality and symbolism in "Simulacra and Simulation" (2016) can address the complexity and ambiguity of social thought. In this respect, poststructuralist thinkers argue that reality cannot be understood objectively and that the opacification of social relations is inevitable. Baudrillard argues that the boundaries

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between reality and simulation are increasingly blurred and that simulation loses its connection with reality while imitating reality. This can complicate people's relationship with reality and lead to confusion. Cultural relativism emphasizes the confusion encountered when trying to understand the values and norms of different cultures. Disagreement and ambiguity between the perspectives of different cultures can arise due to cultural diversity. In this context, critical thinking approaches seek to overcome this confusion by encouraging individuals to approach information and communication critically. Critical thinking develops the ability to question information, evaluate sources and understand different views. Marshall McLuhan's "The Medium is the Message" (1967) discusses how communication technology affects the way society thinks and how it can create confusion. McLuhan argues that communication tools can transform the perceptual and intellectual structure of society and that different forms of media can change the way people think. On the other hand, John Sweller's theory can also be considered in this context (Bowe, 1975). The concept of information overload refers to the situation where the amount of information people encounter in their daily lives exceeds the limits of what can be processed. This situation may cause people to experience difficulties in processing and understanding this information as well as ease of access to information. Cognitive load theory addresses the difficulties people experience when using their mental resources to process and understand information. Overload or complexity during information processing can deplete individuals' mental resources and lead to mental foginess. These theories address different aspects of the concept of the construction of a fuzzy society and try to explain how social, cultural and cognitive factors may contribute to this situation. In political science, the concept of a "confused society" refers to a state of complexity, uncertainty or difficulty in understanding society in the areas of political thoughts, values, ideologies and political communication. The concept is used in political science to describe the loss of intellectual clarity in society due to differences of opinion on political issues, communication barriers, information pollution and ideological diversity. While Marxism, a political and economic theory and movement based on the work of Karl Marx and Friedrich Engels, focuses on the analysis and critique of capitalist society, the term "confused society" refers to the intellectual state of society in a broader context. There may be many connections and overlaps between the two concepts, but a direct concept of a "confused society" is not

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found explicitly within Marxism. Nevertheless, if we consider the potential connections between Marxist thought and the fuzzy society, it seems possible to address the issue as follows:

Ideology and Illusion: Marxism analyzes how ideology is used by the ruling classes of society and how they maintain oppression. In this context, ideology and illusion can cloud the state of mind of society and make it difficult to understand class differences, exploitation and the capitalist system.

Class Conflict and Consciousness: Marxism argues that class conflict plays a central role in the dynamics of society. It argues that in capitalist society the working class is oppressed and serves the interests of the bourgeoisie (owners of capital) for profit. The aim is for the working class to understand this situation and become conscious of it, leading to a more mentally clear society.

Labor Theory of Value and Inequality: Marxism deals with the value of labor and the ownership of the means of production. Issues of inequality and exploitation are among the factors that determine the intellectual state of society. These inequalities can lead to confusion and make it difficult for individuals to understand their own circumstances.

Criticism of Capitalism: Marxism criticizes the capitalist system and emphasizes the problems it creates. These criticisms can encourage questioning of the intellectual structure of society and contribute to the formation of alternative intellectual perspectives.

Social Transformation and Consciousness Raising: One of the main goals of Marxist theory is to promote social transformation and the consciousness of the proletariat (working class). This aims to make the mental state of society clearer and more conscious.

The concept of "The Construction of a Confused Society" refers to a phenomenon that emerges

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as a result of the interaction of issues such as social complexity, media and politics, although it is not known as a specific theory or theoretical framework in the social sciences. The basic principles underlying this concept stem from different theoretical approaches and histories. However, the concept is of great importance for understanding society's understanding and access to information. Understanding this concept is important to reduce societal opacity, recognize manipulation and help individuals develop more critical thinking skills. Across the world, the influence of the media and the development of communication technologies are influencing the construction of an opaque society. The interaction between different cultures, beliefs and opinions leads to the understanding of facts from different perspectives. While the influence of media and politics shapes the way society understands facts, the rapid flow of information brought about by the digital age can also pave the way for the spread of misleading information. In the case of Turkey, historical, cultural and political diversity affects the construction of a confused society. Conflicts between different ethnic groups, cultural perspectives and political views can lead to opacification of facts. The political influence of the media can limit the way society understands facts. At the same time, however, increased information sharing among individuals and the hearing of different voices through the influence of social media can contribute to the consideration of more perspectives.

Conclusion and Recommendations

The concept of building a confused society is a complex and multifaceted issue and requires a continuous effort to increase social awareness and reduce the complexity of meaning. A confused society can lead to communication breakdowns and conflicts. Communication can become difficult; misunderstandings and conflicts can arise because people understand different realities. When society understands facts in different ways, it can negatively affect democratic participation. When people do not have access to accurate information, it can be difficult to make effective political decisions and participate in democratic processes. Cultural and social segregation can undermine unity and lead to cultural or social divisions between different groups. The construction of a confused society is important for political scientists in the formation of social views and the meaning of political participation. How political leaders and parties represent different points of view, how the media reflects political discourses, and how society understands political realities is critical for the analysis of political processes. By

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understanding the construction of an opaque society, political scientists seek to better understand the impact of political campaigns, voter behavior and democratic processes. Political scientists also work to develop political reforms and communication strategies to reduce social opacity and increase access to information.

In this context, the education system is one of the most important solutions for a disoriented society. The education system should emphasize media literacy and enable people to critically evaluate media content. Education and media platforms should encourage people to understand the perspectives of people from different cultures, beliefs and views. At the same time, the media should reflect social diversity by presenting different views and perspectives, and the independence and diversity of media outlets should be promoted. Political leaders and governments should earn the trust of the public through open and transparent information sharing and clear presentation of the facts; verification channels and fact-checking systems should be established to combat fake news and misleading information. In addition, encouraging social dialogue and cooperation between different groups can contribute to the solution of the issue as it can facilitate understanding and reconciliation of different views. The construction of a confused society can be overcome by promoting effective communication, critical thinking and information assessment skills and increasing the intellectual clarity of the society, and measures such as education, media literacy, diversified media presentation, political transparency, fact-checking mechanisms and social dialogue are needed to address the fuzzy society. These steps can contribute to a more understanding, informed and democratic society.

LIMITATIONS

The research is limited to scientific studies that have been conducted worldwide and have been included in the literature.

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